

REGIONAL FEATURES OF FUNCTIONAL GASTROINTESTINAL DISORDERS IN CHILDREN

Temirov Murodjon Telmonovich

Bukhara State Medical Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10997172>

According to pediatric gastroenterologists, about 70% of the child population suffers from chronic constipation [1], however, it should be noted that the true frequency of constipation in children remains unclear, since not all cases of diseases are registered due to the low appeal of parents, especially at the initial stage of the disease. Children "outgrow" the problem of constipation, which is not confirmed by long-term observations: 30-52% of children have symptoms that persist for the next 5 years, about 25% of children continue to suffer from constipation in adulthood [2].

In 95% of cases, constipation is of a functional nature and is the result of malnutrition or food intolerance, decreased motor activity and behavioral causes on the part of both the child and parents. The prevalence of functional constipation is especially high in young children. So, according to G. Iacono et al., it is 17.6%, T.A. Sadovnichaya cites data for the Stavropol Territory – 21-25%, and in Moscow, according to a study by S.I. Erdes, it reaches 41% [3].

The purpose of scientific work was to study the frequency of functional constipation in children of the Bukhara Region in the periods from 2018 to 2020.

Materials and methods

The analysis showed that during the studied period 43,012 sick children were hospitalized in BODMPMC, of which 8.71% were sick children with gastrointestinal diseases (3745 patients). Among all sick children with gastrointestinal diseases (3745), functional constipation accounted for -7.87% (295 patients). A retrospective analysis of 3745 case histories of children who received inpatient treatment in the departments of gastroenterology and surgery of the BODMC from 2018 to 2020 for diseases of the gastrointestinal tract was carried out. During the analysis, 295 case histories of sick children with chronic constipation were selected.

The results of the study showed that the total number of patients hospitalized in BODMC for 3 years amounted to 43012 patients, in 2018 – 12540 (29.2%), in 2019 – 14024 (32.6%) and in 2020 – 16448 (38.2%).

Hospitalization of children for gastrointestinal diseases during the studied period was 3745 (8.7%), in 2018 – 1021 (27.3%), in 2019 – 1246 (33.3%) and in

2020 - 1478 (39.4%), respectively, which indicates an increase in gastroenterological morbidity over 3 years.

All pathology of organic genesis was represented by Hirschsprung's disease, among which boys -16 (80%), and girls - 4 (20%), 5 of them were operated on (25%), and the rest - 15 (75%) were treated conservatively in the surgical department. Among the operated patients, there were 3 boys (18.75%) and 2 girls (40%), respectively.

In the early puberty period, functional constipation becomes chronic and in more than 9.0% of cases, patients also need treatment in a hospital.

By studying the causes of constipation from anamnestic data, 6 main causal and etiological factors contributing to the development of chronic constipation were identified:

- psychosocial maladaptation in 86 (29.1%), included children going to a preschool educational institution, potty training, fear of defecation after an episode of acute stool retention, unfavorable emotional atmosphere in the family, stress, etc.;
- autonomic dysfunction syndrome (SVD) - in 78 (26.5%);
- the alimentary factor, represented by an unbalanced diet and insufficient fluid intake, was found in 57 (19.4%);
- intestinal dysbiosis - 38 (12.9%);
- gastrointestinal form of food allergy - 26 (8.8%);
- inactivity - 10 (3.3%).

Conclusion

Thus, based on the results of the study and the study of the regional characteristics of chronic constipation in the Bukhara region, it was found that chronic constipation accounts for 7.9% of cases among all gastrointestinal pathology in children, when distributed by gender and place of residence, boys living in rural areas aged 4-6 years are more likely to suffer. Functional constipation prevails by origin - 93.2% of cases, among the causal factors, the highest frequency is represented by psychosocial maladaptation and SVD, according to the clinical course 48.5% of all chronic constipation, among hospitalized patients subcompensated.

All this confirms the importance of preventive measures to prevent chronic constipation with children at risk

References:

1. Giannetti E., Sciorio E., Staiano A. Treatment of constipation: Where do we go? // JPGN. -2011.- 53 (2). -53-54.

POLAND

CURRENT APPROACHES AND NEW RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCES

International scientific-online conference

POLAND

2. Iacono G., Merolla R., D'Amico D. et al. Gastrointestinal symptoms in infancy: a population-based prospective study. *Dig Liver Dis* 2005; 37:6: 432–438.
3. Southwell B.R. Treatment of slow transit constipation in children // *JPGN.* 2011. -53 (2). -51-53.

